

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP2. Data collection and visualization framework
T2.2. Set-up of the LOOPER database

Deliverable D 2.1

REPORT ON DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE FRAMEWORK

ANNEX 1: WWW.CROWDMAPPING.EU USER GUIDE

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Responsible partner: IUAV

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1

To start open your browser from your computer, tablet or smartphone and go to www.crowdmapping.eu

Scroll down to reach the part of the page with the link to access the map of the LOOPER Living Lab of your interest.

At this point you can either:

A. Click on the image/name of the LOOPER Living Lab and you will be redirected to the home page of the web app of the city of your interest

or
B. Click on the "Insert geoTAG!" and you will be automatically redirected to the map where you can place the tag

NOTA BENE: with option B, if you don't have your credential saved (automatic log in) you will only be able to try the web app but you will not be able to save any data.

EDITOR USERS AND ADMINISTRATOR USERS GUIDE

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

La sezione di crowdMapping.eu dedicata all'Urban Living Lab di Verona è lo strumento di mappatura web con il quale i membri del laboratorio di progettazione previsto dal progetto europeo "LOOPER" possono raccogliere informazioni su problemi, buone pratiche o elementi significativi della città utilizzando il proprio smartphone.

Ogni "geoTag" è un oggetto localizzato sulla mappa online ed è caratterizzabile con descrizioni e dettagli oltre che con allegati come foto o videoclip.

Per collaborare alla mappatura è necessario essere registrati come membri del LOOPER Urban Living Lab Verona.

[Place geoTAG \(preview\) >](#)

B Browsing
Data access to data allowed only to registered users. Users can browse the geoTag map or query the geoTag archive with custom search criteria. It is also available the link to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.
[Browse the map >](#)

C Editing
GeoTAG placement is allowed only to users with administration or editor roles. Editing allow users to digitize points, lines or polygons on the map and attach to them text and multimedia contents. Editor users can also their own geoTag archive.
[Place geoTAG \(preview\) >](#)

D Settings
Settings are only available to users with administration role. They allow to manage the full geoTag archive, edit application general settings, manage user accounts and geoTAG categories.
[Manage geoTag archive >](#)

If you choosed the image/name from the previous page, you will now find yourself in the home page of the web app (Verona is used for this user manual).

In this page you will have a set of choices:

- A. Log in
- B. Browse the map
- C. Edit your data (both editor and administrator accounts)
- D. Manage every data (only administrator accounts)
- E. Place a geoTAG in preview mode (saving not possible)

NOTA BENE: you always have to log in BEFORE placing your geoTAG otherwise you will not be able to save any data.

The screenshot shows the Safari browser window displaying the website www.crowdMapping.eu. The page title is "LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab". The header includes a "Menu" dropdown, a search bar with the text "chiara.scari", a password field, and a "Log-in" button. A red arrow points to the "Log-in" button. The main content area contains the following text:

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

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Ogni "geoTag" è un oggetto localizzato sulla mappa online ed è caratterizzabile con descrizioni e dettagli oltre che con allegati come foto o videoclip.

Per collaborare alla mappatura è necessario essere registrati come membri del LOOPER Urban Living Lab Verona.

Below the text is a blue button: "Place geoTAG (preview) >".

The page also features three columns of information:

- Browsing**: Data access to data allowed only to registered users. Users can browse the geoTag map or query the geoTag archive with custom search criteria. It is also available the link to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format. Button: "Browse the map >".
- Editing**: GeoTAG placement is allowed only to users with administration or editor roles. Editing allow users to digitize points, lines or polygons on the map and attach to them text and multimedia contents. Editor users can also their own geoTag archive. Button: "Place geoTAG (preview) >".
- Settings**: Settings are only available to users with administration role. They allow to manage the full geoTag archive, edit application general settings, manage user accounts and geoTAG categories. Button: "Manage geoTag archive >".

To log in you have to insert your credential in the top right part of the page. Once you have filled "username" and "password" you can press log in and you will enable the various options of the app. Some options are open both for EDITOR users and ADMINISTRATOR users, while other are open only for ADMINISTRATORS.

NOTA BENE: only participants with a log in can plage geoTAGs autonomously, all other participants can ask administrators of their LOOPER Living Lab if they can add a geoTAG to the map.

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

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Ogni "geoTag" è un oggetto localizzato sulla mappa online ed è caratterizzabile con descrizioni e dettagli oltre che con allegati come foto o videoclip.

Per collaborare alla mappatura è necessario essere registrati come membri del LOOPER Urban Living Lab Verona.

↓6-16

[Place geoTAG »](#)

Browsing
Users can [browse the geoTag map](#) or [query the geoTag archive](#) with custom search criteria.
It is also available the [link](#) to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.

[Browse the map »](#)

Editing
GeoTAG placement is allowed only to users with administration or editor roles. Editing allow users to digitize points, lines or polygons on the map and attach to them text and multimedia contents.
Editor users can also [their own geoTag archive](#).

[Place new geoTAG »](#)

Settings
Settings are only available to users with administration role. They allow to [manage the full geoTag archive](#), edit [application general settings](#), [manage user accounts](#) and [geoTAG categories](#).

[Manage geoTag archive »](#)

Once you successfully log in the page will slightly change, and this is how it will look like.

Firstly we will talk about how to place a geoTAG (step 6 to 16), then there are other interesting options that can be found in the home page but that will be explained later in this guide.

As soon as you select "place geoTAG" from the home page you will be redirected to a map that will ask you if you allow the website to use your current location (this happens only in the desktop version).

You should allow the browser to use your location, in this way the map will automatically move the map to your position.

Once you allowed the device to move to your location, you will see a page like this (with a different placing).

As it is possible to see in the image in the next page there are a set of buttons that can be used to place your geoTAG and to add informations to it.

On top left (dotted blue circle) there is the zoom in and zoom out option. You will find this button also in the tablet/smartphone version, but in that case you can also use your fingers to zoom.

Next to it you will have the ">GPS<" button (dotted green circle) which moves the map to show your current position, not the one of the pin that you placed.

The the button in the dotted blue circle can be used to change from map to satellite image.

This is useful if it is needed to find a specific place using reference points (i.e. square, park)

The pin button (always dotted blue circle) can switch on and off the geoTAGs placed by other users.

If the button is grey it means that the geoTAGs are switched off.

If the button is blue it means that the geoTAGs are switched on.

If the option is switched on it will also show your geoTAGs, not only the ones from other users.

The the button in the dotted blue circle has to be used to choose the type of geometry that you want to use to place the geoTAG.

The “Point geometry” option places a simple point on the map.

To do so it is needed to click (or tap if a smartphone/tablet is used) and the geoTAG will be placed.

11a

The “Line geometry” option places a line, composed by various points, on the map.

To do so it is needed to click (or tap if a smartphone/tablet is used) where you want the line to start, and where you want the line to end and the geoTAG will be placed.

If you want to draw a broken line it is necessary to click the start and end point, but also all the points in which the line changes direction.

To close the line you need to double click on the ending point.

Please see images 11a-11b-11c to view how it works.

11b

11c

The “Polygon geometry” option places an area, composed by various points, on the map.

To do so it is needed to click (or tap if a smartphone/tablet is used) on the position of each vertex which creates the area and the geoTAG will be placed.

To close the polygon you need to double click on the ending point.

Please see images 12a-12b-12c to view how it works.

12c

The “Data & files” button opens a pop-up with a set of fields to fill.

It is not mandatory to fill all the fields but it is kindly recommended to do so, in this way everyone will have a better comprehension of the situation.

NOTA BENE: you can go back and forward between the map and the “Data & files” at any time during the process without deleting what you have done until now.

The first field is "Label".

Here you have to write an extremely short description of the issue/good practice you want to tag.

There is a limit of characters that you can write.

NOTA BENE: you will see this field on the map when you place the geoTAG, because of this the shorter the label the clearer the map will stay.

The second field is “Description”.

Here you can write as much as you want to write more in detail what are you tagging.

The description can be seen when the tag is selected on the general map.

The third field is "Keywords".

Here you can write one, or more, keywords that suit the tag. These can be later used to do some search with a keyword.

The fourth field shows a list of categories that are specific of the LOOPER Living Lab that have been chosen in the beginning.

Here you have to select the category which is most suitable to the geoTAG you are placing.

The fifth field shows a rating list.

This list is needed to point if the geoTAG wants to add a criticality or a good practice (i.e. presence of greenspaces = positive/optimal, traffic = critical).

The last field allows to attach a document (image, pdf, word document, etc.) to the geoTAG.

To do so you need to click on “choose file” which opens a tab from which it is possible to select the file you want to attach.

NOTA BENE: if you are using a smartphone or a tablet by clicking on “choose file” you will also have the option of take a picture with the camera integrated in your device.

Once you select the file you will return to the pop-up and you will see the name of the document you choose in the last field.

As you finish to fill the "Data & files" you can click outside the pop-up and you will return to the map.

Once you completed everything and you are ready to save the geoTAG you must press the "Save" button (blue dotted circle) and this will end the process.

NOTA BENE: THE geoTAG WILL BE SAVED ONLY IF YOU PRESS THE "SAVE" BUTTON

After pressing "Save" you will be automatically redirected to the page you can see above.

This page will show you a preview of the geoTAG you placed and here you have two options (the two blue buttons on bottom right of the map):

- Visualize complete map
- Place other geoTAG

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

Menu - Authenticated user: chiara.scanagatta [End session]

GeoTag Map

Place geoTAG »

Browsing Editing Settings

If you press the “Visualize complete map” button you will be able to view a map of your LOOPER Living Lab with every geoTAG that have been placed by you and by every other user.

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

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[Place geoTAG »](#)

Browsing
Users can [browse the geoTag map](#) or [query the geoTag archive](#) with custom search criteria. It is also available the [link](#) to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.
[Browse the map »](#)

Editing
GeoTAG placement is allowed only to users with administration or editor roles. Editing allow users to digitize points, lines or polygons on the map and attach to them text and multimedia contents. Editor users can also [their own geoTag archive](#).
[Place new geoTAG »](#)

Settings
Settings are only available to users with administration role. They allow to [manage the full geoTag archive](#), edit [application general settings](#), [manage user accounts](#) and [geoTAG categories](#).
[Manage geoTag archive »](#)

As soon as you finished with the geoTAG placement you can go back to the home page where you can find other options that can be used from Editor Account, while others can be only used by Administrator Accounts.

On the top right side of the home page it is possible to see the Menu button (blue dotted circle), which shows a wide range of options (some of which can be found in the bottom part of the home page).

Editor Accounts can use options A-B-C-D.

Administrator Accounts can use every option.

As you click on "browse the geoTAG map" you will be redirected to a page in which you will see the area interested by the LOOPER Living Lab you are working with.

The map will show you every geoTAG already placed by other participants. You will also see your geoTAGs if you already placed some.

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

Authenticated user: chiara.scanagatta [End session]

GeoTag search

Attachment:

Description:

Timestamp:

Label:

Keywords:

Category:

GeoTag search

#	Att.	Label	Description	Keywords	Timestamp	Category
5		Chiesa di S.Nicolò	Chiesa di S.Nicolò	Chiesa	2018-02-07T15:07:57	Elementi urbani

First < > Last

Browsing

Users can browse the geoTag map or query the geoTag archive with custom search criteria. It is also available the link to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.

Browse the map >

Editing

GeoTAG placement is allowed only to users with administration or editor roles. Editing allow users to digitize points, lines or polygons on the map and attach to them text and multimedia contents. Editor users can also their own geoTag archive.

Place new geoTAG >

Settings

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Manage geoTag archive >

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If you move to the “query the geoTAG archive” you will find a set of options to find specific geoTAGs from the list of all the ones placed.

From here you can search by one of the following options:

- attachment
- description
- timestamp
- label
- keywords
- category

or you can choose to search with two or multiple of them.

LOOPER Verona ULL - GeoTag archive manager

Authenticated user: chiara.scanagatta [End session]

GeoTag archive manager

GeoTag search

#	Label	Description	Category	Rating	Keywords	Timestamp	Owner
5	Chiesa di S. Nicolò	Chiesa di S. Nicolò	Elementi urbani	Positive	Chiesa	2018-02-07T15:07:57	giovanni.borga

Rows per page: 10

Browsing

Users can browse the geoTag map or query the geoTag archive with custom search criteria. It is also available the link to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.

Browse the map -

Editing

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Place new geoTAG -

Settings

Settings are only available to users with administration role. They allow to manage the full geoTag archive, edit application general settings, manage user accounts and geoTAG categories.

Manage geoTag archive -

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If you open the “geoTAG archive manager” you will see:

- your geoTAG (if you have an Editor account)
- every geoTAG (if you have an Administrator account)

Here you can modify every aspect of the geoTAGs that have been placed by clicking on the pencil in the first column of the list.

ADMINISTRATOR USERS GUIDE

Categories manager

This is the list of available categories to use to classify geoTags.

Category	Order number	Color
Strade e mobilità	1	DarkOrange
Spazi verdi	2	LimeGreen
Qualità dell'ambiente urbano	3	RoyalBlue
Elementi urbani	4	OrangeRed
		LightCoral

First 1 Last

Browsing
Users can browse the geoTag map or query the geoTag archive with custom search criteria.
It is also available the link to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.

Editing
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Editor users can also their own geoTag archive.

Settings
Settings are only available to users with administration role. They allow to manage the full geoTag archive, edit application general settings, manage user accounts and geoTAG categories.

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THIS OPTION IS FOR ADMINISTRATOR USERS ONLY.

The “categories manager” can be used to change the categories of geoTAGs from which Editor users can choose while placing the geoTAG.

As in the “geoTAG archive manager” to change something you have to click on the pencil.

To add a category fill the fields in the last row and at the end click on the green tick

LOOPER Verona UrbanLivingLab

Menu - Authenticated user: chiara.scanagatta [End session]

Account manager

Username	Password	Email	Name	Surname	Role
chiara.martinelli	*****	chiara@legambienteverona.it	Chiara	Martinelli	Administrator
chiara.scanagatta	*****	c.scanagatta@stud.uav.it	Chiara	Scanagatta	Administrator
daniele.madella	*****	daniele@studiomadella.com	Daniele	Madella	Editor
giovanni.borga	*****	giovanni@borga.it	Giovanni	Borga	Administrator
giuseppe.campagnari	*****	campagn@gmail.com	Giuseppe	Campagnari	Editor
lorenzo.albi	*****	l.albi@legambienteverona.it	Lorenzo	Albi	Editor
massimiliano.condotta	*****	condotta@uav.it	Massimiliano	Condotta	Administrator
mattia.battaioi	*****	mattia@legambienteverona.it	Mattia	Battaioi	Administrator
silvia.pernechele	*****	silvia@legambienteverona.it	Silvia	Pernechele	Editor

First < 1 > Last

[Manage groups >](#)

Browsing

Users can browse the geoTag map or query the geoTag archive with custom search criteria. It is also available the link to download the full geoTAG archive in geoJSON format.

Editing

GeoTAG placement is allowed only to users with administration or editor roles. Editing allow users to digitize points, lines or polygons on the map and attach to them text and multimedia contents. Editor users can also their own geoTag archive.

Settings

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THIS OPTION IS FOR ADMINISTRATOR USERS ONLY.

Here you can add and modify users.

To modify a user click on the pencil, here you can also change the account type (Editor or Administrator).

To add and account fill every field of the last row and validate the account by clicking on the green tick.

THIS OPTION IS FOR ADMINISTRATOR USERS ONLY.

The "configuration manager" can be used to change the settings of the pages of the LOOPER Living Lab that you are in.

As in the previous example to modify something you need to change the pencil button in the first column.

NOTA BENE: it is better if you do not make changes in this page to keep the layout of every LOOPER Living Labs the same.